

Decision Analysis

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To cite this article:

William N. Caballero, Roi Naveiro, David Ríos Insua (2021) Modeling Ethical and Operational Preferences in Automated Driving Systems. Decision Analysis

Published online in Articles in Advance 29 Oct 2021

. <https://doi.org/10.1287/deca.2021.0441>

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Modeling Ethical and Operational Preferences in Automated Driving Systems

William N. Caballero,^a Roi Naveiro,^b David Ríos Insua^b

^aUnited States Air Force Academy, Colorado Springs, Colorado 80840; ^bInstitute of Mathematical Sciences, 28049 Madrid, Spain

Contact: william.caballero@us.af.mil, <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-8432-4680> (WNC); roi.naveiro@icmat.es,

 <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-5748-9658> (DRI)

Received: March 21, 2021

Revised: July 6, 2021

Accepted: August 26, 2021

Published Online in Articles in Advance:
October 29, 2021

<https://doi.org/10.1287/deca.2021.0441>

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Abstract. Whereas automated driving technology has made tremendous gains in the last decade, significant questions remain regarding its integration into society. Given its revolutionary nature, the use of automated driving systems (ADSs) is accompanied by myriad novel quandaries relating to both operational and ethical concerns that are relevant to numerous stakeholders (e.g., governments, manufacturers, and passengers). When considering any such problem, the ADS's decision-making calculus is always a central component. This is true for concerns about public perception and trust to others regarding explainability and legal certainty. Therefore, in this manuscript, we set forth a general decision-analytic framework tailorable to multitudinous stakeholders. More specifically, we develop and validate a generic tree of ADS management objectives, explore potential attributes for their measurement, and provide multiattribute utility functions for implementation. Given the contention surrounding numerous ethical concerns in ADS operations, we explore how each of the aforementioned components can be tailored in accordance with the stakeholder's desired ethical perspective. A simulation environment is developed upon which our framework is tested. Within this environment we illustrate how our approach can be leveraged by stakeholders to make strategic trade-offs regarding ADS behavior and to inform policymaking efforts. In so doing, our framework is demonstrated as a practical, tractable, and transparent means of modeling ADS decision making.

Funding: Work supported by the European Union's Horizon 2020 Trustonomy Project [Grant 815003] and a Fundación BBVA project. D. Ríos Insua is supported by the AXA ICMAT Chair of the Institute of Mathematical Sciences and the Spanish Ministry of Science [Program MTM2017-86875-C3-1-R]. This research is also partially supported by the European Office of Aerospace Research and Development (EOARD) and the Air Force Office of Scientific Research (AFOSR) Dynamic Data and Information Processing (DDIP) program.

Keywords: automated driving systems • ethics • multicriteria decision analysis • self-driving vehicles • explainability

1. Introduction

Fueled by breakthroughs in machine learning and computational hardware, the past decade has witnessed the rapid development of *automated driving systems* (ADSs). These are anticipated to revolutionize human transportation by improving safety, emissions, and passenger comfort (Milakis et al. 2017). However, the growth of ADS technology is outpacing our collective ability to integrate it into society. This is best illustrated by Audi's attempted marketplace

introduction of the A8 (Lindland 2020). Equipped with its Traffic Jam Pilot system, enabling automated operations at low speeds, the A8's entrance into the European market was scheduled for 2020, but these plans were rescinded and delayed indefinitely because of unresolved ethical and regulatory concerns. To mitigate such issues in the future, stakeholders (e.g., manufacturers, owners, regulators) must be able to tailor an ADS's underlying decision-making model to incorporate operational, ethical, and regulatory

perspectives. In so doing, meaningful comparisons can be made across a broad range of settings to incorporate varying viewpoints. Transparency surrounding the ADS's preferences is enhanced, and thoughtful design and regulation can be achieved. Such is the focus of this manuscript.

The nuanced nature of vehicle autonomy is a complicating factor. That is, ADSs are classified within the six-level taxonomy of driving automation (Society of Automobile Engineers 2018). Level 0 describes vehicles with no automated capacity, and levels 1–5 represent vehicles with increasing automated features culminating in fully automated, level 5 ADSs. Aside from these pinnacle-level ADSs, automated vehicles require human input when operating outside of their specified operational design domain (ODD). The solicitation of this input in lower-level ADSs introduces additional applied ethics concerns—for example, the transfer of accident liability from manufacturer to driver (Caballero et al. 2021b). ADS behavior in such situations is determined by a fundamental issue: the modeling of ADS preferences. This entails two major complications. The first is standard and refers to balancing multiple objectives (e.g., travel time versus fuel consumption), whereas the second is more unique; it concerns ethics and other societal impacts.

As is generally the case with revolutionary technologies, the widespread adoption of ADSs is accompanied by numerous moral uncertainties, cogently summarised by the European Commission (2020). Lin (2016) presents multiple vignettes illustrating ethical dilemmas associated with ADSs that must be addressed to ensure their integration into society. Unfortunately, in addressing these dilemmas, decision makers are forced to grapple with unenviable ethical quandaries. One example, discussed by Ríos Insua et al. (2021), refers to a *fundamental dilemma* in level 3 and 4 ADSs. If a dangerous situation is predicted, the driver is expected to be alert and ready to assume vehicular control; however, if the driver is actually distracted and the ADS transfers control, the consequences could be catastrophic. Under such situations, it is thus unclear whether it is preferable for the ADS to transfer control or retain it. In the former, drivers assume the risk associated with their distraction, whereas the ADS is forced to make life-and-death

decisions outside of its ODD in the latter. Other ethical problems akin to this dilemma are frequently represented and explored as *trolley problems*. Although their utilization has been criticized (Basl and Behrends 2020), such problems are widely used as an analogy in the study of ADS ethics. Notably, Awad et al. (2018) developed an online experimental platform called the Moral Machine wherein users repeatedly resolve trolley problems to gain insight into societal and ethical preferences, as well as their relationship to myriad cultural factors.

A universal consensus over ADS-programmed morality is unlikely. Notwithstanding the foregoing, herein we develop a generic multiattribute utility model for ADS management that allows designers, owners, and policy makers to tailor ADS behavior and decision making according to their own ethical framework. Because our approach is rooted in decision theory, the selected objectives, attributes, and structure of the multiattribute utility determine the ethical perspective adopted. The decision analysis framework provided herein can accommodate multiple ethical viewpoints (Keeney 1984); however, we primarily focus on the consequentialist¹ and deontological² paradigms, as well as a subset of their refinements (e.g., rule utilitarianism). In this manner, the framework provided herein allows for ethical, operational, and regulatory trade-offs to be developed and studied in a computationally tractable manner. This approach leverages the value-focused thinking paradigm (Keeney 1992), as demonstrated by Dees et al. (2013), Merrick and Grabowski (2014), and Simon et al. (2014).

Moreover, this research furthers the collective study of ADS ethics and provides a means, in the far term, to inform national-level regulation. Conversely, the near-term aim of this research is the provision of decision-analytic support for ADS design and operation. As argued by the European Commission (2020), such support may refer to diverse ADS operations, including both long-horizon (e.g., routing between two cities) and short-horizon (e.g., emergency maneuvering) actions. This is important to stress because ethical research has traditionally focused on a subset of the latter (i.e., emergency response). In juxtaposition, our research enables a more complete analysis of ADS ethics.

More specifically, this manuscript enables the analysis of decisions in general situations by providing the following.

- A generic tree of potential ADS management objectives, including their corresponding attributes
- A generic multiattribute utility model to translate the aforementioned objectives into quantified assessments of stakeholders' preferences and risk profiles
- A discussion of ethical issues in ADS management solvable with tailored utility functions
- A simulation environment to assess the effectiveness of the utility functions introduced to explore ethical and operational ADS issues
- A demonstration of how the provided framework can be utilized to invoke desired ADS behavior, inform policy making, and settle liability concerns

That is, we propose a general model serving as an initial catalogue for multitudinous stakeholders that is tailorable to their specific interests. Relying on the proposed objective tree, an organization or an individual may select some of the objectives and exclude others. Moreover, they may also include additional objectives of particular relevance to them. Such an approach is inspired by earlier work on preference modeling in specific domains such as aviation safety (Rios Insua et al. 2019), antiterrorism analysis (Keeney 2007b), homeland security decisions (Keeney and von Winterfeldt 2011), and cybersecurity risk management (Couce-Vieira et al. 2020). This research provides a template for other controversial applications of automation (e.g., military command and control) as well (Caballero et al. 2021a).

The remainder of this manuscript is structured as follows. We first provide a generic objective tree for ADS management. Ideally, this would be shown to stakeholders who would use it to construct their own tailored objective tree. For each of the objectives, potential attributes to assess achievement are provided. Once the objectives and their attributes are specified, we build a utility function to assess impacts; a generic model is provided whose specific functional form is obtained through a series of questions resolved by the stakeholder. We discuss how the stakeholder's ethics can be encoded in an ADS control algorithm by careful selection of the preference model's functional form, the selected objectives, the associated attributes, and the objective weights. The effects of such

selections on accident liability are also explored. Finally, we perform experiments in our simulated environment to better understand trade-offs between different utility function specifications, and we illustrate the model's functionality for policy making.

2. Structuring ADS Objectives

Different stakeholders may pursue different ADS objectives. The owner of a logistics fleet may be interested in maximizing profit while preserving corporate reputation. A private owner may desire a comfortable trip that avoids traffic jams and prioritizes speed. An insurance company might be more concerned with safety. Alternatively, stakeholders may have common objectives but measure them with different attributes (e.g., depending on their ethical perspective).

In this section, we elaborate on how our general framework was developed, provide a comprehensive list of objectives affecting varied stakeholders, and present attributes for the proposed objectives. We discuss how these elements can be combined to form a tailored preference model for the stakeholder in Section 3. For much of this manuscript we adopt a normative approach to decision analysis; however, as discussed in Section 3.2, we also allow for the utilization of descriptive approaches in order to comply with alternative ethical and developmental perspectives.

2.1. Developing a General Framework

ADS operations entail a variety of consequences that depend on the specific setting. Routine operations incur consequences associated with monetary costs, comfort, and time. Hazardous situations may incur reputational effects (e.g., harming a manufacturer's branding) and, potentially, infrastructure damage or casualties. These consequences can be tracked by the relevant stakeholder based on the attributes associated with the stakeholder's fundamental objectives (Keeney 2013).

Our problem is contextualized through a stakeholder who desires to develop an ADS decision support strategy. This entails assessing the potential impacts of all relevant events and determining how the control policy guides the ADS. As previously mentioned, the objectives may vary by stakeholder. Objectives may also vary by country and domain (e.g., passenger transportation, emergency healthcare,

commercial logistics). Furthermore, the objectives can vary based on the time horizon: short-term, emergency control objectives typically differ from long-term control objectives in a safe and permissive environment. To accommodate all these settings, we present a generic objective tree that stakeholders may utilize when considering a problem. Section 3 discusses how a stakeholder may desire the utilization of multiple models depending on the environmental conditions.

The process used to build our objective tree consisted of an in-depth review of the multiple-objective driving literature, as well as the ADS literature more generally, to identify commonly considered impacts. We also reviewed related regulatory, ethical, and safety literature to complete the initial list of objectives, merging those that were similar. Adopting the terminology of Keeney (2007a), our focus was on determining the fundamental objectives for ADS decision support, stemming from lists of (mostly fundamental) objectives identified in the literature. A means-ends objective network was not explicitly utilized; instead, a mind map was used to group the identified objectives. These were then aggregated into a tree to facilitate construction of our ADS preference model.

The names and definitions of these categories were made as generic as possible. Doing so aligns our framework with the standard requirements discussed by Keeney and Gregory (2005): objective trees should be *comprehensive, measurable, nonoverlapping, relevant, unambiguous, and understandable*. Our initial version was assessed in-depth and complemented by the technical partners of our sponsoring project, Trustonomy.³ The technical partners have varying backgrounds. They include representatives from automotive manufacturers, ADS information technology providers, and driving training organizations as well as transportation psychologists and other transportation researchers. The objective tree was validated by the Trustonomy steering committee, which included additional manufacturers, insurers, and regulators. Feedback implied the requisite conditions were satisfied.

The lowest nodes in the tree provide q dimensions used to (1) describe the ADS driving policy and ascertain its validity, (2) assess the implementation of the driving policy, and (3) support the construction of the driving policy itself. Each of these scales should be

quantified with an *attribute*, allowing each consequence to be represented as a vector of attribute levels $c = (c_1, c_2, \dots, c_q)$. The specific value of q is, as previously mentioned, stakeholder dependent.

2.2. Proposed Objective Tree

Our initial search covered the main ADS frameworks, which provided catalogues of concepts analogous to our objectives. This search included a review of legal documents published by ADS manufacturers (e.g., Waymo LLC 2020), corporate strategic documents (Uber Advanced Technologies Group 2018), governmental regulatory strategies (e.g., U.S. National Highway Traffic Safety Administration 2016, European Parliamentary Research Service 2018, U.S. Congressional Research Service 2020, U.S. Department of Transportation 2020), think tank reports (e.g., Gibson 2016, Blumenthal et al. 2020), as well as public surveys and feedback from empirical trials (e.g., Bonnefon et al. 2016, Daziano et al. 2017). Other references in the multiobjective driving literature were also reviewed (e.g., Chen et al. 2013; Dovgan et al. 2013, 2014; Nandi et al. 2015; Li and Czarnecki 2018; Zhou et al. 2020). The analysis of these documents revealed recurrent goals from a set of overarching categories. However, these goals did not conform with the standard decision analytic requirements. Most documents implicitly provided a set of important ADS impacts but not a single comprehensive list. Similarly, many of the implied objectives exhibited a degree of overlap, suggesting the usefulness of categorization.

Herein, we utilized the aforementioned information to construct a hierarchy of objectives and impacts for the ADS setting that complied with best practices discussed in Section 2.1. In our context, comprehensiveness and nonoverlapping correspond with the careful addition of novel concepts, whereas relevance and understandability are related to translating ADS impacts for the stakeholder.

Our generic ADS objective tree is provided in Figure 1. We completed an in-depth validation of this hierarchy, arriving at the following conclusions. With regard to comprehensiveness, we evaluated existing categories of impacts to ensure their coverage by our objectives. Solving eventual overlaps entails creating more abstract concepts; however, we contend that the efficacy of doing so should be addressed on a case-

Figure 1. Generic ADS Objective Tree

by-case basis for each stakeholder. Assuming an event may involve impacts on several objectives, one must ensure that impacts included in one objective are not included in another. Objectives are named in general terms, instead of industry-specific jargon, to mitigate ambiguity and poor understandability. The comprehensiveness of the objectives is illustrated by including aspects relevant to a broad array of stakeholders.

The remainder of this section further describes the rationale behind each identified objective.

2.2.1. Performance Objectives. The performance objectives refer to aspects of ADS operations that do not include a safety component. These may include the ADS’s mechanical performance as well as travel time and passenger (driver) comfort.

2.2.1.1. Fuel Consumption. The reduction of fuel consumption is one of the most common goals pursued in ADS research and development (e.g., Prakash et al. 2016, Tsugawa et al. 2016). In such settings, the intent is to optimize the ADS’s trajectory and speed management systems to attain the greatest fuel economy. ADS operations are optimized to maximize cost

savings. The natural attribute associated with this objective can be related in monetary terms by utilizing the fuel consumption rate and the unit price of gasoline.

2.2.1.2. Trip Duration. As with most transportation tasks, it is generally desirable in the ADS setting to minimize travel time. This objective is often at odds with fuel consumption. Time is the most natural attribute associated with this objective that, in some instances, may be transformed into a monetary value (e.g., when the stakeholder is a logistics company).

2.2.1.3. Passenger Comfort. Most stakeholders desire the maximization of passenger comfort (i.e., of all individuals inside the ADS). However, depending on the specific context, it may be desirable to maintain the passenger comfort level within some prespecified interval, entailing the nonmonotonicity of preferences over comfort. For example, in level 3 and 4 ADSs, a driver who is too comfortable may be unable to effectively take control of the vehicle in emergency situations because of drowsiness. Likewise, a ground-based logistics company may require its drivers to perform additional tasks during transit that could be

inhibited by maximizing comfort unconditionally. Multiple perspectives may be adopted regarding the attributes associated with this objective; see Section 2.3.1 for further discussion.

2.2.2. Safety Objectives. Safety objectives refer to aspects of ADS operations that explicitly include a safety component. These objectives have a character distinct from the performance objectives, given their emphasis on physical protection.

2.2.2.1. Individuals Inside and Outside ADS. An ADS accident can affect a wide array of actors including the ADS passengers, individuals in nearby vehicles, or pedestrians in the driving scene. Therefore, when adopting a consequentialist ethical perspective, the ADS control algorithm should minimize harm to these individuals (i.e., fatalities and physical injuries). Alternatively, when adopting a deontological ethical perspective, we assume an associated theory of justice (i.e., what constitutes a moral distribution of risk) is embraced. For example, the stakeholder may abide by deontic egalitarianism⁴ or libertarianism.⁵ This perspective accords with that of Keeney (1984) for the application of deontological ethics within decision analysis (i.e., by maximizing respect for life). Depending on the specific ethical perspective adopted, natural attributes may or may not be available to measure this objective; we discuss such physical harm attributes more thoroughly in Section 2.3.2.

2.2.2.2. Vehicle Damage. An ADS accident will inevitably cause some sort of damage to itself and, potentially, to other nearby vehicles. These impacts are undesirable, and stakeholders would like to minimize them. Vehicle damage can be measured monetarily.

2.2.2.3. Infrastructure Damage. As with the actors in the driving scene, the surrounding infrastructure can be affected by an ADS accident. This objective expressly considers the minimization of such impacts (e.g., damage to buildings, power lines, and public spaces generally) and can be measured monetarily.

2.2.2.4. Environmental Impact. Auto manufacturers and governments worldwide have expressed an interest in lessening the effects of automobile operations

on the environment. This objective directly translates to the ADS setting. Environmental impacts may arise in a variety of manners at both global and local levels. For example, the minimization of greenhouse gas emissions can be related to lessening the global environmental damage caused by ADS operations. This objective is often complementary to fuel consumption reduction, but it is also affected by driving style and weather conditions, among numerous other factors (European Environmental Agency 2016). Alternatively, local impacts may include risks to nearby wildlife and their habitats. Whereas these environmental impacts generally have intuitive natural attributes (e.g., amount of carbon emissions), they can often be converted to monetary values as well (Schulze and Kneese 1999).

2.2.3. Reputation Objectives. Because an ADS must often select actions independent of real-time human concurrence, the impact of its actions on a population's trust is critically important. The reputation objectives consider both trust in an individual manufacturer and trust in ADS technology writ large. Associated attributes are nonmonetary and are further discussed in Section 2.3.3.

2.2.3.1. Automotive Manufacturer. This objective concerns impacts on trustworthiness linked directly to the automotive manufacturer. This perspective is adopted in lieu of proxies; however, impacts on trustworthiness are not always faithfully measured via monetary attributes.

2.2.3.2. Views of ADS in Society. We also include the societal impact of ADS operations—namely, an accident involving an ADS may impact public opinion. Such incidents affect a population's trust in automated vehicles at a conceptual level. As with automaker trustworthiness, monetary attributes may not faithfully measure this objective.

2.3. Attributes for Nonmonetary Objectives

Several of the identified objectives are not measurable in monetary terms. We describe herein how a stakeholder may proceed with each. To infer these attributes, a decision analysis often involves the identification of the

most likely and most dangerous scenarios. These what-if scenarios must be comprehensive, covering all feasible impacts related to the relevant objectives, stakeholders, assets, and activities.

In our ADS setting, subject-matter experts within the Trustonomy project team helped in devising such a set of scenarios; these were subsequently validated in workshops with ADS specialists. Once identified, these scenarios were quantified for use in our preference model. When available and implementable, this involved the identification of a natural attribute associated with the objective. Otherwise, either a constructed attribute was developed or a proxy was identified for the corresponding objective (Keeney 1992). As discussed in Section 3, the ethics of the decision maker should typically be considered when selecting among the available attributes for a given objective.

2.3.1. Comfort Attributes. Whereas passenger comfort in an ADS is a subjective experience, physical and physiological measurements can be utilized for its assessment. Beggiato et al. (2018) illustrate one such example wherein a smart band was employed to measure heart rate, eye-tracking glasses monitored blink frequency and pupil dilation, and camera and pressure mats monitored body movements.

Such human-based metrics are particularly convenient because many are already collected by the ADS’s driver state monitoring system that assesses the driver’s ability to take control of the vehicle (Ríos Insua et al. 2021). Table 1 presents a constructed attribute that can be utilized in this context for human-based measurements that are perceived from cameras and pressure sensors. Thresholds in the constructed

attribute are derived from the results of Beggiato et al. (2018). If the ADS is properly equipped, other physiological measures (e.g., pupil dilation) can also be incorporated.

Alternatively, multiple authors have shown that passenger comfort is correlated with the physical movements of the vehicle. Bellem et al. (2016) considered three different *driving styles* (everyday, comfortable, and dynamic), each associated with increasing levels of discomfort. The authors asked drivers to control a vehicle under their subjective perception of each style when executing multiple maneuvers in varied settings (e.g., rural and urban). Analysis revealed a set of discriminating metrics for driving styles in the following maneuvers.

- Accelerating from a nonzero speed
 - *Longitudinal acceleration*: Mean longitudinal acceleration over the monitored time period
 - *Acceleration jerk*: Rate of longitudinal acceleration when pressing the gas pedal
 - *Deceleration jerk*: Rate of longitudinal deceleration when releasing the gas pedal
 - *Longitudinal quickness*: Mean longitudinal acceleration divided by the change in longitudinal velocity
- Lane change
 - *Lateral acceleration*: Mean acceleration over the monitored time period
 - *Lateral quickness*: Lateral velocity divided by lateral offset
- Following a vehicle at nonzero speed
 - *Headway distance*: Bumper-to-bumper separation between the ADS and the lead vehicle
- Decelerating to a moving target

Table 1. Example of Passenger Comfort Constructed Scale

Rank	Description of passenger comfort-related behavior
1	Characteristics include nondistress blink frequency (< 0.2 blinks per second), a typical standardized vertical shoulder position (z-score > -0.4), and low application of standardized seat mat pressure (z-score < 0.2).
2	Exactly one of the following exceeds Rank 1 thresholds: blink frequency, standardized vertical shoulder position, or standardized seat mat pressure.
3	Exactly two of the following exceed Rank 1 thresholds: blink frequency, standardized vertical shoulder position, and standardized seat mat pressure.
4	Blink frequency, standardized vertical shoulder position, and standardized seat mat pressure all exceed Rank 1 thresholds.

- *Longitudinal acceleration*: The same as accelerating from a nonzero speed
- *Longitudinal quickness*: The same as accelerating from a nonzero speed
- *Minimum headway distance*: The same as following vehicle at nonzero speed

These factors are, broadly speaking, applicable to determining driving styles (and the associated comfort level) in both rural and urban settings. Thus, their values can also be utilized as proxy attributes to determine a passenger's comfort level in the ADS. Acceleration, jerk, and quickness values are negatively associated with comfort, whereas headway distances are positively associated with passenger comfort (Bellem et al. 2016).

If proxy attributes are deemed undesirable by the stakeholder, alternative constructed attributes can be formed based on the aforementioned ADS movements and their relationship to driving styles. The classification discussed herein can be utilized, but alternatives exist in the literature (e.g., Møller and Haustein 2013). Conversely, other attributes to infer passenger comfort can be constructed based on weighted root mean square acceleration (Du et al. 2018) or Likert scales (Siebert et al. 2013, Hartwich et al. 2018).

2.3.2. Physical Harm Attributes. When adopting a consequentialist ethical perspective, stakeholders are concerned with the outcomes of their actions. With regard to an ADS's impact on an individual's health, these outcomes correspond to fatalities and injuries. Minimization of fatalities can be assessed with a natural attribute—for example, the number of fatalities. The statistical value of life (VSL) can also be used to aggregate fatalities within the multiattribute model (Viscusi and Aldy 2003).

Conversely, injuries can be assessed with both natural and constructed attributes, depending on the specific stakeholder. For example, the International Classification of Diseases published by the World Health Organization (WHO) (2018) provides a list of numerous types of injuries, diseases, and disorders together with several of their features. These classifications encompass thousands of ailments and injuries. Such a categorization is useful as a discrete, natural attribute. However, depending on the

stakeholder, a simpler attribute may be sufficient. Indeed, risk analysis for transportation-related accidents typically distinguishes between major and minor injuries (Ríos Insua et al. 2019); these can be used as two natural attributes. For aggregation purposes, the value of statistical injury (VSI) is a reasonable alternative (Viscusi and Gentry 2015).

If such natural attributes for injuries are deemed inappropriate by a specific stakeholder, there exist suitable constructed attributes as well. Several methods enable the creation of an ordinal scale to assess the severity of physical or mental injuries (Hasler et al. 2012). Notable examples include the Injury Severity Score, the Global Assessment of Functioning, and the WHO Disability Assessment Schedule (Ustün et al. 2010). From these metrics and excluding fatality values, Couce-Vieira et al. (2020) develop an exemplar constructed attribute that can also be utilized to assess the impact of injuries in an ADS accident.

When adopting a deontological ethical perspective, stakeholders are not concerned with the outcomes of their decision but with its inherent ethical worth. For example, from a deontological perspective, the stakeholder may desire to maximize the respect for life an action shows to the individuals involved in the incident. An attribute for such an objective corresponds to the amount of risk each action places on the associated individuals. A deontic egalitarian would desire to select the action that most equally distributes the probability of injury or death; these probabilities can be used as the corresponding attributes. In fact, Keeney (1984) discusses how risk measures (i.e., probabilities) can be effectively used in a generic deontological framework for life-and-death choices. He also discussed therein how constructed attributes can be developed to achieve a similar effect. Contingent upon how the stakeholder defines respect, probabilities can be defended as a natural or proxy attribute. Henceforth, we assume respect for life is defined in terms of risk probabilities and classify it as a natural attribute.

2.3.3. Attributes for Reputation Objectives. Although intuitive, monetary measures may not faithfully assess reputational gains or losses. This is well illustrated in recent studies of reputation damage. Hubbard and Selersen (2016) consider a company that suffers a

cyberattack; the authors show that insufficient evidence exists to strongly link data breaches to stock prices. Given the reliance of ADSs on interconnected computational systems, this cybersecurity example is directly applicable. However, it also shows the potentially tenuous relationship between reputation and some of its intuitive proxy measures (e.g., stock price).

With regard to assessing reputation monetarily, the Ford Pinto case in the 1970s is a particularly salient example (e.g., see Birsch and Fielder (1994)). As a result of Ford's negligent management of fuel system design defects, its cumulative sales and profitability decreased; however, effects on its stock price were more nuanced (Ermann et al. 1978). Therefore, although monetary measures may be utilized as proxies for reputation, it is unclear to what degree profitability and sales are simultaneously affected by other exogenous factors. Until further research is conducted to statistically describe the relationship between ADS reputational effects and monetary measures, other constructed and proxy attributes may be preferable.

Whereas some scholars from organizational theory utilize an overall measure of reputation (e.g., Fombrun 2012), other authors advocate for a more attribute-specific approach (e.g., Jensen et al. 2012). Accordingly, we contend it is preferable to view reputation through the four categories identified by Carpenter and Krause (2011). The following nomenclature is adapted to the ADS context to facilitate understanding: *moral reputation* (in reference to the treatment of stakeholders), *compliance* (regarding legal and social norms), *performative* (execution of assigned functions), and, finally, *adaptability* (ability to modify behavior in novel circumstances).

For such socially constructed concepts, attributes are commonly built by interviews with stakeholder representatives or surveying a representative sample of the considered audience (van Riel and Fombrun 2007). In this manner, one can apply the principles presented in Keeney and Gregory (2005) to build a constructed scale. As with the physical harm attributes, Couce-Vieira et al. (2020) provide a constructed scale that abides by these tenets while leveraging the aforementioned categorization. This attribute can be tailored to many stakeholders: a manufacturer would

primarily consider its reputation with customers, whereas a regulator would be concerned with the views of the general public. However, the thresholds and scenarios for each stakeholder must be reviewed and modified in accordance with its particular reputational interests.

Alternatively, as proxy attributes, a stakeholder may leverage the salience of ADS incidents in news, media, and social networks or the cost of handling the reputation impact of the incident. A variety of natural language processing tools are commercially available to collect and measure the resonance and sentiment of such discussions.

2.4. Summary

Table 2 summarizes the ADS management objectives and attributes that can be included in our ADS decision support analyses. The objectives are ordered sequentially according to their introduction in Section 2.2. Generally speaking, it is advisable to leverage natural attributes whenever available. If natural attributes are not available or the stakeholder deems them inappropriate, then a constructed scale should be utilized. Alternatively, if the stakeholder perceives the constructed attribute to be too ambiguous or insufficient for any other reason, then a proxy attribute should be utilized. We refer the reader to Keeney and Gregory (2005) for further discussion. Table 2 facilitates the choice of attributes for each objective by providing a summary of potential options.

3. Preference Model Development

The generic model presented herein can explicitly account for operational and ethical concerns from the vantage point of myriad stakeholders. As discussed by Keeney (1984), a decision-analytic perspective can accommodate numerous moral viewpoints; however, doing so requires tailoring the decision analysis to the desired perspective (e.g., selecting objectives in accordance with deontological ethics). We do not advocate for any specific point of view but provide a framework tailorable to the stakeholders' ethical outlook and their perspectives on operational concerns. As previously discussed, the ethics associated with a multiattribute utility function are primarily determined by (1) the preference model's functional form,

Table 2. Summary of Objectives and Attributes

Objective	Natural attribute	Constructed attribute	Proxy attribute
Min. fuel consumption	Monetary units		
Min. trip duration	Temporal units		
	Monetary units		
Min. driver/passenger discomfort		Yes	ADS movement
Min. injuries of individuals inside (outside) ADS	Number of injuries	Yes	No. in hospital
Min. fatalities of individuals inside (outside) ADS	Number of fatalities	Yes	
	VSL		
Max. respect for inside (outside) ADS	Prob. of death/injury	Yes	
	VSI		
Min. damage to ADS	Monetary units		
Min. infrastructure damage	Monetary units		
Min. environmental impact (global/local)	Monetary units		
	Emissions		
Min. harm to manufacturer reputation		Yes	Media salience
Min. harm to societal perceptions		Yes	Media salience

(2) the selected objectives, (3) the associated attributes, and (4) the objective weights utilized.

Each decision made by the ADS is characterized by some lottery, F , over a set of rewards, $f = (f_1, \dots, f_n)$. In this notation, the lottery gives an outcome f_j if state j occurs; each outcome is associated with a vector of rewards, $c_j = (c_{j1}, c_{j2}, \dots, c_{jq})$. The probability of occurrence for any state j equals p_j . We alternatively adopt notation common in both normative and descriptive decision theory, in their respective applications, and assume the lotteries and attribute values are known (Keeney and Raiffa 1993, Wakker 2010). Regardless of the approach adopted, $V(F)$ signifies the value of the lottery (e.g., its expected utility).

In our context, the choice between normative and descriptive approaches, as well as multiple others in the development of the stakeholder's preference model, is significantly affected by the desired ethical perspective. Therefore, we begin this section by discussing how unique ethical issues affect decisions in our ADS setting. We then discuss the relationship between different ethical perspectives and the preference model's structure; the section closes by discussing how objectives, attributes, and objective weights can be refined for specific stakeholders based on the underlying planning horizon.

3.1. Ethical Issues

One of the most contentious topics in ADS research relates to decision making in potentially fatal

situations, particularly the ethics associated with automated decision making. This moral quandary is often succinctly considered via simple trolley problems (Jarvis 1976). In such scenarios, a decision maker is asked to choose between two certainly fatal outcomes of a morally ambiguous nature. In its adaptation to ADS, a trolley problem states that a collision is unavoidable, and it poses a question of the following form: Is it preferable to swerve left and strike five adults or to swerve right and strike a child? The ethics of ADSs making decisions in such environments is well studied (Lin 2016, Awad et al. 2020, Keeling 2020) but remains hotly contested. This is, in part, because no universally accepted solution exists. Any judgment on the morality of an ADS's decision depends on the ethical perspective adopted (Gerdes and Thornton 2016).

This tension is perhaps best illustrated by the empirical results of Bonnefon et al. (2016). Participants in the authors' study largely agreed that ADSs programmed with utilitarian⁶ ethics were more moral, but they preferred to purchase ADS programmed to act in a self-protective manner. In this example, a degree of ethical egoism⁷ permeates the consumers' otherwise utilitarian ethos. That is, when assuming a passenger role, participants preferred a self-protective ADS, despite its inability to maximize utility for all participants; conversely, they desired a self-sacrificing ADS to be utilized by others. This deviation also permeated the individuals' perspectives on regulation:

consumers negatively viewed laws mandating ADSs adopt a utilitarian perspective.

It can therefore be observed that ethics plays a central role in the development of an ADS's preference model. Thankfully, decision analysis can tractably model varied ethical viewpoints and moral trade-offs (Keeney 1984). By purposeful selection of its preference model structure, objectives, and attributes, a stakeholder is able to encode the ADS with one ethos or another. Hybrid ethical perspectives can also be constructed via selection of the objective weights.

3.2. Preference Model Structure

In selecting the preference model structure, the stakeholder must first decide whether to adopt a normative or descriptive approach. Both are sensible depending on the desired ethical perspective and the stakeholder's beliefs. By utilizing a normative approach, varied consequentialist and deontological ethical perspectives can be adopted (Keeney 1984). However, in adopting a descriptive approach, the stakeholder is able to effectuate a unique rule-utilitarian perspective: an ADS's ethical value calculus should mirror that of a human.

Via its sensing abilities and computational algorithms, an ADS in the future will have improved situational awareness and reaction times compared with a human driver. From a normative perspective, this allows for the correction of paradoxical choices that violate the axioms of expected utility. Conversely, from a descriptive perspective, it allows ethical human preferences, as measured in a controlled setting (i.e., not under duress), to be encoded directly into the ADS. It is well known that such preferences may not be rational as defined by the expected utility axioms; a descriptive theory of choice allows these preferences to be faithfully regressed. Whereas most decision analysts would still argue in favor of expected utility theory, numerous psychologists and ethicists would disagree. Likewise, from a practical perspective, it has been noted that for ADSs to be trusted, their passengers must understand their decision calculus. To gain this trust, a stakeholder (e.g., a manufacturer) has two options: (1) convince the driver of expected utility theory's sensibility or (2) model choice behavior descriptively in accordance with empirical data.

Therefore, to keep our framework as general as possible and allow for varied stakeholder beliefs and ethics, we address both perspectives in turn.

Each objective discussed in Section 2.2 lends itself to a natural ordering that is disconnected from the other objectives. Therefore, should a normative approach be adopted, it is natural to assume that the preferences of most stakeholders will satisfy mutual preference and utility independence (Keeney and Raiffa 1993). This implies that the multiattribute utility function is of multiplicative form such that

$$1 + \theta u(f_j) = \prod_{k=1}^q (1 + \theta \theta_k u_k(f_j)).$$

In this equation, $u(f_j)$ is the multiattribute utility function, and $u_k(f_j)$ is the component utility function of attribute k for outcome f_j . Likewise, we have $\theta > -1$ and $\theta_i \in [0, 1]$. The value of the lottery is $V(F) = \mathbb{E}_j(u(f_j))$.

From an ethical perspective, any stakeholder characterized by consequentialist thought can be modelled using a certain θ -value (i.e., via multiplicative or additive utility). On the other hand, this is often not the case from a deontological perspective. If a stakeholder is characterized by a deontological ethos for some objective and $\theta \neq 0$, then the marginal utility of this objective may change given different values of another objective's attribute; that is, the consequences affect the stakeholder's utility. This logic is often better suited for consequentialism, implying that additive utility may be more appropriate. However, this ultimately depends on how exactly the objectives and attributes have been defined.

There also exist ethical implications associated with the component utility functions. Specifically, functions characterized by constant absolute risk aversion (CARA) are arguably more appropriate for a deontological ethos than are other utility functions. This is due to the absolutism often linked with deontology. Alternatively, consequentialism is more flexible in this regard and can adopt numerous functional forms without caveat; for example, see the egalitarian and libertarian approaches of Schulze and Kneese (1981) and the consequentialist CARA utility models for lifetime utility (Yaari 1965, Bommier 2006). The specification of risk attitudes in the component utility

functions is interesting in its own right as well. By varying the ADS's risk attitude, the utility of an action changes. Therefore, from a consequentialist perspective, the selected risk attitude determines how the ADS understands the effect of its actions and is the foundation upon which ethical consequences are determined.

For their part, the objective weights, θ_k , inform the collective ethics of the stakeholder by weighing the importance of specific objectives relative to the others. In so doing, they also enable hybrid ethical perspectives to be adopted wherein disparate objectives may be approached via distinct ethos. Additional impacts of the objective weights are discussed in Section 3.4.

Alternatively, a descriptive theory of choice may be utilized to account for varied ethical and practical concerns. Such an approach is logical if the stakeholder desires to effectuate a rule-utilitarian ethos or if it is pessimistic regarding the driver's confidence in the expected utility model. There exist multiple descriptive theories of choice (Stewart et al. 2006, Kontek and Lewandowski 2018, Kellen et al. 2020) that enable such modeling by accounting for empirical violations of normative assumptions. However, cumulative prospect theory (CPT) is arguably the most robust and well known (Tversky and Kahneman 1992); see Caballero and Lunday (2019) for a more thorough discussion in this regard. Multiple extensions of CPT have adapted it to a multiattribute setting as considered herein. These adaptations adopt either a holistic or attribute-specific perspective on the reference point or decision weights, respectively (Bleichrodt and Miyamoto 2003, Bleichrodt et al. 2009). The latter perspective is particularly beneficial in our context as it allows for more intuitive stakeholder reasoning and understanding.

Assuming the preference conditions of Bleichrodt et al. (2009) are satisfied, to calculate a lottery's value in the attribute-specific method with additive utility, the outcomes are rank ordered and separated into gains and losses for each component utility. That is, for each attribute, the indices of the lottery's outcomes must be reordered based on the corresponding utility function value, and these indices are segmented into two sets based on their value relative to each objective's reference point. For every attribute

$k = 1, 2, \dots, q$, there is a reference point, r_k , such that any utility value greater than or equal to r_k is considered a gain and a loss otherwise. For an arbitrary attribute, A_k , the rank-order indices are given by $\{\rho_{k1}, \rho_{k2}, \dots, \rho_{kn}\}$. Without loss of generality, we assume the outcomes associated with m_k indices are losses, whereas the remaining ones are associated with gains. With these definitions, the CPT value of the lottery can be defined as

$$V(F) = \sum_{k=1}^q \left(\sum_{i=1}^{m_k} \pi^-(p_{\rho_{ki}}) u_k^-(f_{\rho_{ki}}) + \sum_{i=m_k+1}^n \pi^+(p_{\rho_{ki}}) u_k^+(f_{\rho_{ki}}) \right)$$

such that

$$\begin{aligned} \pi^-(p_{\rho_{k1}}) &= W_k^-(p_{\rho_{k1}}), \\ \pi^-(p_{\rho_{ki}}) &= W_k^-(p_{\rho_{k1}}, \dots, p_{\rho_{ki}}) - W_k^-(p_{\rho_{k1}}, \dots, p_{\rho_{k(i-1)}}), \\ & \quad 1 < i \leq m_k, \\ \pi^+(p_{\rho_{ki}}) &= W_k^+(p_{\rho_{ki}}, \dots, p_{\rho_{kn}}) - W_k^+(p_{\rho_{k(i+1)}}, \dots, p_{\rho_{kn}}), \\ & \quad m_k + 1 \leq i < n, \\ \pi^+(p_{\rho_{kn}}) &= W_k^+(p_{\rho_{kn}}), \end{aligned}$$

where W_k^+ and W_k^- are probability weighting functions, and $u_k^-(\cdot)$ and $u_k^+(\cdot)$ are loss and gain utilities, respectively, for each objective. Under these assumptions, the relative differences in an attribute's utility are encoded within its respective utility function; we refer the interested reader to Zank (2001) for an alternative multilinear representation and associated utility independence results.

The probability weighting functions account for empirical results indicating that humans systematically overweight low probabilities and underweight high probabilities. There exist multiple functional forms for these functions (e.g., Prelec 1998, Gonzalez and Wu 1999, Cavagnaro et al. 2013); however, they all exhibit the characteristic inverse sigmoid shape predicted by the aforementioned empirical results. Furthermore, the separation of outcomes into gains and losses is a unique feature of CPT that allows it to account for *loss aversion*, the empirical pattern showing that losses loom larger than the corresponding gains (Tversky and Kahneman 1991). This feature yields the characteristic sigmoid-shaped utility function described by Tversky and Kahneman (1992). Bleichrodt et al. (2009) provide further guidance regarding the selection of these functional forms and

provide conditions for when a common attribute-weighting function exists.

3.3. Choosing Objectives and Attributes

From the comprehensive list of ADS objectives identified in Section 2.2, the incumbent stakeholder should choose those objectives that are relevant to its ADS management problem. The discussion in Section 2 provides guidance on how varied ethos can be adapted to each objective. In developing a tailored set of objectives, the stakeholder may eliminate some and add others.

As mentioned in Section 2.2, objectives were intentionally phrased broadly to maintain applicability to a wide array of stakeholders. To ensure the decision analysis adequately represents the stakeholder's intent, it may be the case that the objective verbiage should be sharpened for clarity. This is typically not the case with operational objectives (e.g., trip duration) but is more prevalent in the objectives intended to limit human suffering.

For example, consider the objective seeking to minimize harm to individuals outside of the ADS. Phrased in this manner, the objective is appropriate for a deontological or a consequentialist perspective. However, by explicitly phrasing the objective's intent to show equal respect for each individual's life, a more nuanced deontological ethos can be utilized (i.e., deontic egalitarianism). Such an ethical approach would also likely entail merging the health objectives for individuals inside and outside of the ADS. The associated attribute would correspond to the disparity of risk to health incurred by these individuals due to a given action.

Alternatively, by keeping separate the safety objectives for individuals inside or outside the ADS, one can accommodate contrasts in different consequentialist paradigms. Consider the egoistic and egalitarian ethical perspectives. An egoistic ethical perspective will prioritize driver self-preservation and is morally justified in doing so. This is juxtaposed by the egalitarian ethos that implies moral action requires the equitable sharing of positive or negative effects.

Moreover, ethical imperatives (i.e., forbidding or mandating an action) that constrain behavior are a feature of deontology. These imperatives can be modeled by assigning infinite utility values (positive or

negative) to the appropriate action for the given objective. For example, if no action should be taken that endangers a child, then a negative infinite utility can be assigned to this outcome. On the other hand, if the action space is too large to make this strategy feasible, the deontological imperatives can be modeled as inequalities, and a constrained optimization problem can be solved to determine the ADS's behavior.

3.4. Objective Weights

As previously mentioned, the objective weights (θ_k) inform the conceptual ethos utilized by the ADS. However, it is important to consider at a more granular level how the specification of these weights can be used to tailor ADS behavior. This section explores how differing values of θ_k can be leveraged to develop situation-specific preference models and accommodate varied perspectives on liability. Whereas a single set of utility weights can be leveraged, this implicitly assumes that the stakeholder views long-horizon and short-horizon decision problems to be of a similar character. This need not be the case, and in what follows, we describe how a stakeholder can proceed under such assumptions.

An ADS must make both short- and long-horizon decisions in a dynamic environment. This implies that the same set of objectives are considered in multiple related but distinct decision-making contexts. Likewise, the relative importance of one objective with respect to another may not be static because the decision-making environment is itself constantly evolving. A suite of distinct preference models may be required depending on these factors. Although other specifications are possible, we shall consider three preference models: (1) long-horizon, (2) short-horizon under standard conditions, and (3) short-horizon under emergency conditions.

Decision making in the long-horizon model may be primarily concerned with the trip from a macroscopic level. For example, decisions encountered may pertain to the ADS's route, the environmental emissions, and vehicle maintenance concerns (e.g., selecting routes causing less wear on essential components). The repercussions of such decisions are often associated with vehicle performance instead of safety concerns (e.g., travel time is often of primary interest when routing a cross-country trip). Therefore, if a

consequentialist ethos is adopted, it is appropriate for the objective weights related to operational concerns to exceed those associated with safety.

Short-horizon models entail more immediate decisions (e.g., steering wheel control and accelerator input). Whereas such decisions generate minor consequences on some operational objectives (e.g., fuel consumption and trip duration), they may have a much greater impact on safety-related objectives, particularly under emergency conditions. It is therefore logical for a consequentialist stakeholder to weigh the safety objectives relatively higher than others.

Under this construct, it becomes readily apparent how the weights can be used for regulatory purposes. That is, objective weights are generally constructed by considering a comprehensive set of value trade-offs (Keeney and von Winterfeldt 2011). A regulatory stakeholder can therefore mandate minimum value trade-off thresholds for manufacturers and operators. Moreover, liability standards can be based on these trade-offs and weights. The degree of liability inherited by the operator and manufacturer in a given driving mode can be based on how conservatively the ADS behaves in emergency situations toward different entities (e.g., pedestrians and infrastructure).

From a consequentialist perspective, the ratio of the objective weights can be used to partially infer the ADS's ethics. For example, if a much higher weight is assigned to protecting the ADS passengers compared with individuals outside of the vehicle, then an egoist ethos is being adopted. Should the converse hold, then the ADS is adopting an altruistic ethical perspective. Alternatively, if the weights are approximately equal, an egalitarian ethos is being utilized.

In a similar manner, the effect of objective weights on liability can also be readily observed, especially if the weights are tailorable by different stakeholders. Consider the following: Should we assume that a normative framework is utilized to model ADS preferences, then it is highly likely that a government regulator would desire to limit the range of objective weights that could be specified in ADS operations. Such regulation allows the government to specify legal restrictions to protect its citizens. Responding to this regulation, an ADS manufacturer is likely to sell its vehicles with recommended baseline weight settings, and it is conceivable that the ADS operator would be empowered to

tailor these to its needs. However, by adapting the objective weights, the operator may incur more liability (e.g., if speed is prioritized over safety), especially if the ADS's algorithms are modified beyond its legal limits.

4. Case Study

This section illustrates how a stakeholder can utilize our generic utility model to explore the impact of varied parametric settings on ADS behavior in a simulated environment. That is, we investigate the impact that an ADS's utility function has in terms of multiple performance measures to facilitate stakeholder tuning. This approach may be seen as a dual to the Moral Machine experiments (Awad et al. 2018). Whereas those experiments presented potential consequences to assess and infer individual preferences, we directly assess preferences and explore their consequences through simulation experiments.

Herein, we adapt the simulation environment of Ríos Insua et al. (2021). The simulation can be broadly characterized as a level 5 ADS driving along a two-lane road wherein a variety of obstructions (e.g., pedestrians or obstacles) may appear. The appendix summarizes the novel elements introduced to explore our generic ADS utility model as well as details about both the physical setting and preference model adopted. For illustrative purposes, we assume that the ADS has perfect sensing capabilities and has certain knowledge about obstacles and pedestrians in the driving scene. In a more realistic setting, uncertainty exists over these quantities, and predictive models, such as those developed by Ríos Insua et al. (2021), should be incorporated accordingly.

In these examples, we adopt a consequentialist-normative perspective. As an illustration of the objectives presented in Table 2, we consider trip duration, harm to individuals inside the ADS, and harm to individuals outside the ADS, but recall that our discussion could extend to other choices of the provided objectives. The experiments highlight the efficacy of the proposed scheme by undertaking computational tests that showcase the ADS's performance.

We perform two blocks of experiments. The first illustrates that our framework produces reasonable outputs, establishes a benchmark, and explores trade-offs. In particular, it explores the trip duration versus safety and the passenger-centric versus altruistic

safety trade-offs (i.e., safety of individuals inside versus outside the ADS). Alternatively, the second block of experiments illustrates how liability questions can be addressed by utilizing our proposed framework.

4.1. Benchmark and Safety Trade-off Experiments

Assuming the perspective of an auto manufacturer having additive multiattribute utility, the first set of experiments explores how different weight configurations (i.e., $\theta_k, \forall k \in \{1, 2, \dots, q\}$) affect the values of the component utilities. As our environment evolves in a probabilistic manner, we perform 200 simulations with roads of equal length to measure relevant quantities.

For a fixed inside safety weight, Figure 2 depicts histograms of the average trip duration and outside safety component utilities over the 200 simulations. As expected, higher trip duration weights yield greater trip duration component utility values (Figure 2(a)). However, these gains are costly because the outside safety weight must decrease accordingly; in turn, this reduces the outside safety component utility (Figure 2(b)).

Figure 3 helps us better understand this trade-off. Figure 3(a) illustrates that larger trip duration weights induce higher average speeds. The resulting effect is obvious because the trip duration component utility benefits from higher speeds. However, increasing the trip duration weight and, thereby ADS speed, also makes accidents more likely (Figure 3(b)). Note that accidents are associated with situations wherein control of the vehicle is suboptimal. This does not

necessarily cause harm to individuals in all instances. Yet if accidents are more likely, physical harm is also more likely, as Figure 2(b) suggests.

A similar trade-off exists between passenger-centric and altruistic safety. This can readily be observed by fixing the trip duration weight and varying the inside safety weight. This, in turn, affects the outside safety weight because these values must sum to 1. Table 3 depicts that as more weight is placed on inside safety, greater inside safety component utilities are induced. However, also note that the outside safety component utility decreases.

These results confirm the existence of two important trade-offs: trip duration versus safety and passenger-centric versus altruistic safety. To further explore them, we assess the impact of different combinations of weights over safety and trip duration. Panels (a) and (b) of Figure 4 illustrate the trade-off between trip duration and the total number of injuries and fatalities, respectively. For a fixed inside safety weight, we simulate operations over 200 additional roads of the same length with different trip duration weights. These figures depict means and two standard deviations across all simulations. It can be observed that the greater the trip duration weight, the faster the ADS travels—but at the expense of passenger and pedestrian safety.

Similarly, the trade-off between the number of injuries and fatalities affecting individuals inside and outside the vehicle is illustrated in Figure 5, (a) and (b),

Figure 2. (Color online) Trip Duration and Outside Safety vs. Trip Duration Weight for Fixed Inside Safety Weight

Note. (a) Average trip duration utility; (b) average outside safety utility.

Figure 3. (Color online) Average Speed and Number of Accidents vs. Trip Duration Weight for Fixed Inside Safety Weight

Note. (a) Average speed; (b) number of accidents.

respectively. In this case, for a constant trip duration weight, a larger inside safety weight implies greater protection to the ADS passengers but less protection to pedestrians at the driving scene.

4.2. Liability and Regulation

A main advantage of the proposed multiattribute framework is that it sheds transparency on the decision-making process implemented during the design and production of ADSs. Utilizing our framework, regulators can undertake in-depth simulations of various configurations until they arrive at socially acceptable results. Such configurations can be mandated by law or recommended as industry standards for auto manufacturers.

As an example, we illustrate how this framework can be leveraged for liability concerns. Assume a regulator has set some safety criteria that must be met by any ADS for it to operate on public infrastructure. The consequentialist-normative perspective of Section 4.1 is once more adopted. The safety criteria do not distinguish between individuals inside and outside

the vehicle (i.e., both are equally weighted) and can be expressed as follows: *the mean plus two standard deviations of injury and fatality totals per X miles should not be greater than 1.4 and 0.25, respectively.* From this, the regulator wishes to determine a recommended industry standard for the ADS objective weights.

When simulating ADS operations, different values of the objective weights can be analyzed, and the regulator can determine whether each combination meets the safety criteria. Figure 6(a) shows that if the inside safety weight is fixed at 0.1, trip duration weights greater than or equal to 0.2 do not meet the regulator’s criteria. With this in mind, trip duration weights below 0.2 could be further explored in order to identify the maximum weight fulfilling the safety constraints. In this particular case, a trip duration weight of 0.1 is admissible.

Having completed the analysis, the regulator recommends this weight combination with accompanied tolerances for manufacturer adoption. The weights for inside safety, outside safety, and trip duration are 0.1, 0.1, and 0.8, respectively. However, an auto manufacturer determines it can gain market share by allocating more weight to inside safety while keeping the trip duration weight constant, thereby decreasing the outside safety weight.

Put concretely, suppose that an inside safety weight of 0.7 is selected. In this scenario, if an injury or fatality occurs, a natural question would be whether the auto manufacturer is liable. To make this

Table 3. Mean Plus/Minus Two Standard Deviations of Component Utilities for Fixed Trip Duration Weight of 0.2

Inside safety weight	Inside safety utility	Outside safety utility
0.01	-0.16 ± 0.01	-0.044 ± 0.008
0.2	-0.011 ± 0.004	-0.080 ± 0.009
0.7	-0.004 ± 0.002	-0.23 ± 0.02

Figure 4. (Color online) Safety vs. Trip Duration Trade-offs

Note. (a) Total number of injuries vs. trip duration; (b) total number of fatalities vs. trip duration.

determination, a simulation of the particular weight configuration could be undertaken to ascertain whether the results fall inside or outside the prescribed safety bounds. Figure 6(b) shows that, in this particular example, the selected weights do not meet the regulator’s criteria, and thus the manufacturer could reasonably be deemed liable. Indeed, Figure 5(b) illustrates that an inside safety weight of 0.7 reduces the risk of the vehicle’s occupants but with a correspondingly increased risk to pedestrian safety.

4.3. Discussion

The results in this section illustrate both the soundness and efficacy of the proposed framework. Section

4.1 demonstrates the logical consequences induced by objective weight variations and their associated trade-offs. Likewise, Section 4.2 illustrates how our generic utility functions can be leveraged to not only control ADS movements on roadways but also address broader topics concerning, for example, regulatory and legal concerns.

Section 4.1 focused on trade-offs induced when a subset of trip duration and safety objectives are considered. However, when more objectives from Table 2 are utilized, additional trade-offs are expected to emerge (e.g., environmental impact versus trip duration). It is likely that these trade-offs will not be binary in nature but will include complex interactions.

Figure 5. (Color online) Passenger-Centric vs. Altruistic Safety Trade-offs

Note. (a) Injuries inside vs. outside ADS; (b) fatalities inside vs. outside ADS.

Figure 6. (Color online) Average Number of Injuries and Fatalities vs. Trip Duration Weight

Note. (a) Inside safety weight of 0.1; (b) inside safety weight of 0.7.

Likewise, the nature of these trade-offs may depend on the adopted ethical perspective and the corresponding attributes. Further analyses of these trade-offs in a higher-fidelity driving simulator is therefore a promising area of future inquiry.

Whereas the liability example in Section 4.2 explicitly pertains to an auto manufacturer deviating from recommended industry standards, it can be extended to numerous other settings. For example, an analogous procedure can be utilized if other stakeholders (e.g., drivers or logistics providers) are empowered to modify ADS objective weights as well. In such a scenario, our liability discussion naturally extends to another societal concern: insurance rate setting. If our framework is adopted in future ADSs, insurance rates may not be based on ADS occupants but the driving style induced by the selected objective weights. In this manner, policy prices may change dynamically as the ADS operator modifies these weights.

The incorporation of additional objectives from Table 2 further enriches potential analyses of this form. The provided set of objectives allows a regulator to simultaneously consider environmental, safety, infrastructure, and ethical regulations. Akin to the aforementioned extension of liability concerns to the insurance industry, the effects of regulatory action may be far-reaching. However, by utilizing the framework advocated herein, these effects are more tractable and transparent. In this manner, our framework is broadly applicable and enables the management of numerous activities to include ADS control and regulation, among others.

5. Conclusion

Herein, we developed a generic framework of ADS preference modeling based on value-focused thinking. We provided a thorough exposition of potential objectives and their corresponding attributes, as well as a generic multiattribute utility model to translate these attribute values into preference relationships. We explored the effects of different ethical perspectives on each of these components and described how hybrid moral frameworks can be constructed accordingly. Multiple ethical perspectives were considered. Nevertheless, a more thorough examination of alternative moralistic perspectives is a promising, and perhaps necessary, area of future research for our framework to be utilized in the development of real-world policy.

Aside from advancing the theoretical aspects of our framework, we also illustrated its soundness and efficacy in a simulated environment. We highlighted how our model can be used to systematically assess trade-offs related to ADS performance and inform the regulation of ADSs more generally. In so doing, we have established the decision-analytic perspective as a transparent, tailorable, and tractable approach to both ADS system management and regulation.

This research provides the foundation upon which future debates on ADS ethics, regulation, and control can occur. Even when equipped with our framework, stakeholders will still need to decide which of the

described ethical frameworks is utilized. We illustrated how normative approaches can adopt varied ethoses in ADS operation; however, one can argue that the imposition of a normative approach on drivers who disagree with (or misunderstand) it is associated with its own moral dilemmas (Howard 1980). Descriptive theories may face a similar challenge if their parameterization is imposed on drivers via average empirical values. Moreover, even the provision of default descriptive parameters may prove controversial. The CPT reference point for the fatality objective is an exemplar; that is, stakeholders would decide a default reference fatality value to determine gains/losses. Myriad opinions in this regard likely exist, and depending on how the stakeholder communicates its actions, the resolution may generate a significant reaction from the public or the courts.

Therefore, although we have provided the structure necessary for stakeholders to take purposeful action, it is evident that opportunities for future research abound. The modeling of ethical and operational ADS preferences remains an active area of inquiry, and the framework developed herein provides a systematic means for its exploration.

Disclaimer

The views expressed in this paper are those of the authors and do not reflect the official policy or position of the United States Air Force, the Department of Defense, or the United States Government.

Appendix. Simulation Environment

This section specifies the simulation environment used in this manuscript. The environment is adapted from Ríos Insua et al. (2021), who model decision support for level 3 and 4 ADSs, to globally assess the proposed ADS preference modeling mechanism in a level 5 ADS. We begin by describing how the driving environment is configured and proceed to detail how the controller is implemented. Although simplified, the logic remains the same in more realistic scenarios; the core components would merely be replaced by their real-world counterparts. For example, information from relevant perception systems would be incorporated to inform probabilistic estimates.

A.1. Driving Environment Configuration

The driving environment configuration describes the road and vehicle attributes as well as trajectory and utility assumptions. Parameters are reconfigurable as illustrated by the experiments in Section 4.

A.1.1. Road Configuration. The ADS moves along a two-lane straight road decomposed into cells of equal length.

A.1.2. Vehicle Configuration. A level 5 ADS operates in automated mode. It is able to select a speed (s_t) based on the number of cells advanced per time interval: 0 (i.e., stopped), 1, 2, or 3. Speed choices are transmitted immediately at the beginning of the time interval. It may also vary its trajectory, moving to the adjacent lane in an attempt to avoid obstacles. The number of persons within the vehicle is a hyperparameter selected by the modeler that may vary between 0 and 4. In our experiments, we consider four passengers. Notice that the results may change if the number of passengers is set to a different value.

A.1.3. Environment. Two types of objects may appear in the driving scene:

- A rock may cover one cell in one of the lanes. The driver can stop to avoid colliding with it (i.e., choose speed 0); once stopped, the rock is cleared from the cell, and the vehicle may restart. Alternatively, the vehicle may change lanes to avoid the obstacle.

- A puddle can also cover one cell in one of the lanes.

Table A.1 reflects the probabilistic dynamics of the obstacles in each lane; the stochastic appearance of these obstacles in the next cell (Y_{t+1}) is conditioned on obstacles in the current cell (y_t). For example, after a rock, the road will necessarily be clean because $p(\text{Rock} | \text{Clean}) = 1$.

We further enrich the simulation environment with pedestrians. The number of pedestrians in the t -th cell (p_t) follows a zero-inflated Poisson (ZIP) distribution with probability π and parameter μ . That is, we have $p_t \sim \text{ZIP}(\pi, \mu)$. In our experiments, $\pi = 0.6$ and $\mu = 2$.

Via its sensors, the ADS can assess the number of pedestrians in the next cell, as well as the presence of an obstacle. This information is available at the time of making a speed-and-lane decision.

A.1.4. Accidents. Within each cell of each lane an accident may take place if an obstacle is present. The occurrence of an accident is modelled as a Bernoulli random variable with probability p_A . This random variable depends on the speed of the vehicle, the obstacle present, and the number of pedestrians in the scene. An accident is defined as a situation in which vehicle control is lost,

Table A.1. Probabilistic Evolution of Y_{t+1} (Columns) Given y_t (Rows)

	Rock	Water	Clean
Rock	0	0	1
Water	0	0.4	0.6
Clean	0.1	0.1	0.8

Table A.2. Accident Probability

	$s_t = 0$	$s_t = 1$	$s_t = 2$	$s_t = 3$
Rock	0	0.15	0.25	0.35
Skid	0	0.05	0.1	0.15
>3 pedestrians	0	0.1	0.15	0.2
1, 2, or 3 pedestrians	0	0.05	0.075	0.1

and individuals are potentially harmed (inside and/or outside the vehicle). Clearly, the more complex the driving scene, the higher the probability of an accident. Thus, this probability depends on the presence of obstacles in the road and the number of individuals outside the vehicle (i.e., see Table A.2). When two types of obstacles appear in the same cell, the probability is combined additively. For instance, if the ADS crosses a cell with a rock and more than three pedestrians at $s_t = 1$, the accident probability is 0.25.

Depending on the obstacle(s) that produced the accident, we distinguish between five types of accidents that are more or less harmful for the individuals outside or inside the vehicle: a crash with rock (type 0), a skid with a puddle (type 1), an accident only involving pedestrians (type 2), a crash with a rock in the presence of pedestrians (type 3), and a skid with a puddle in the presence of pedestrians (type 4).

A.1.5. Injuries and Fatalities for Individuals Outside.

Conditioned on an accident occurring, the number of injuries i_t and fatalities f_t affecting individuals outside the vehicle is modelled through a multinomial distribution with probability vector $(r_i(s_t), r_f(s_t), 1 - [r_i(s_t) + r_f(s_t)])$, wherein both the probabilities $r_i(s_t)$ of injury and $r_f(s_t)$ of fatality depend on s_t . Furthermore, these probability vectors also depend on the accident type. For example, an accident produced by a crash with a rock is potentially more harmful to the pedestrians than one produced by a skid. Specific values of these probability vectors are given in Table A.3.

A.1.6. Injuries and Fatalities for Individuals Inside.

Conditioned on an accident, the number of injuries i'_t and fatalities f'_t affecting individuals inside the vehicle are modelled through a multinomial distribution with probability vector $(z_i(s_t), z_f(s_t), 1 - [z_i(s_t) + z_f(s_t)])$, wherein both $z_i(s_t)$ and $z_f(s_t)$ depend on s_t . For example, if there are q passengers inside the ADS, the number of injuries and fatalities affecting individuals inside is

$$(i'_t, f'_t, q - (i'_t + f'_t)) \mid \text{accident} \\ \sim \text{Mult}\left(q, [z_i(s_t), z_f(s_t), 1 - [z_i(s_t) + z_f(s_t)]]\right).$$

As before, these probability vectors depend on the accident type. Specific values are presented in Table A.4.

Table A.3. Fatalities and Injuries Probabilities Affecting Individuals Outside the ADS Given Accident

	Accident type	$s_t = 0$	$s_t = 1$	$s_t = 2$	$s_t = 3$
$r_i(s_t)$	0	0	0.007	0.010	0.030
$r_f(s_t)$	0	0	0.003	0.005	0.008
$r_i(s_t)$	1	0	0.004	0.007	0.027
$r_f(s_t)$	1	0	0.001	0.003	0.006
$r_i(s_t)$	2	0	0.010	0.020	0.050
$r_f(s_t)$	2	0	0.007	0.009	0.010
$r_i(s_t)$	3	0	0.015	0.025	0.056
$r_f(s_t)$	3	0	0.012	0.014	0.016
$r_i(s_t)$	4	0	0.010	0.020	0.050
$r_f(s_t)$	4	0	0.007	0.009	0.010

A.1.7. Preference Model. The utility function is defined so that its value increases with the ADS's speed. The ADS desires to avoid collisions and skids (for safety reasons), minimize trip duration, and minimize harm to individuals (inside and outside the vehicle).

The multiattribute utility function is modeled from a consequentialist-normative perspective. Three objectives are considered, with their associated attributes in parentheses: trip duration (minutes), safety of individuals inside (number of injuries and fatalities), and safety of individuals outside (number of injuries and fatalities). Weights are assigned to each component and are combined in an additive fashion. Note that, in this instance, the ADS does not weigh fatalities and injuries distinctly but considers them as collective descriptors of the safety objectives.

It is assumed that the ADS strictly prefers trips of shorter duration; higher speeds provide greater utility. In particular, each cell crossing at speeds 0, 1, 2, and 3 provides utilities -1 , 0.5 , 1 , and 2 , respectively. In addition, any accident negatively affects trip duration because of the associated time to recover. This is modelled through a utility of -6 . Conversely, the other two objectives correspond with injuries and fatalities. If a person is injured, the utility is -30 ; if he or she is killed, the utility is -100 .

Component weights are used to assess the trade-offs between safety and trip duration and between self and societal damage. The assessment of a trip's section is computed by summing the utilities over its cells.

A.1.8. Simulating the Driving Environment. To simulate the environment, we select a road size (e.g., 200 cells). The first cell is initialized as clear (i.e., no obstacles present). Thereafter, we deduce the presence of puddles and rocks based on Table A.1. The presence of persons at various cells is then simulated as well.

A.2. Model Implementation

Within the above-mentioned environment, we implement a driving decision-making controller based on the following models.

Table A.4. Fatality and Injury Probabilities Affecting Individuals Inside the ADS Given Accident

	Accident type	$s_t = 0$	$s_t = 1$	$s_t = 2$	$s_t = 3$
$z_i(s_t)$	0	0	0.012	0.019	0.045
$z_f(s_t)$	0	0	0.008	0.008	0.005
$z_i(s_t)$	1	0	0.009	0.012	0.036
$z_f(s_t)$	1	0	0.006	0.008	0.012
$z_i(s_t)$	2	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
$z_f(s_t)$	2	0	0.000	0.000	0.000
$z_i(s_t)$	3	0	0.013	0.022	0.053
$z_f(s_t)$	3	0	0.009	0.011	0.013
$z_i(s_t)$	4	0	0.012	0.019	0.045
$z_f(s_t)$	4	0	0.008	0.008	0.005

A.2.1. Environment Monitoring. We assume that individuals and obstacles outside the ADS are sensed perfectly one cell in advance. In addition, speed and lane decisions are transmitted instantaneously at the beginning of each cell. Thus, no forecasting is needed. However, should we have uncertainty about individuals and obstacles outside of the ADS at decision time, probabilistic forecasts should be included (e.g., Ríos Insua et al. 2021).

A.2.2. Trajectory Planning. At each cell, the ADS senses the presence and type of obstacle within the next cell, as well as the number of pedestrians. With this information, speed and lane decisions are made, maximizing expected utility.

A.2.3. ADS Control. Using the previously defined elements, the trip is managed as follows.

1. The ADS enters into the first cell. The utilities associated with each attribute, as well as the weights of each utility component, are prespecified. The speed-and-lane decision for the first cell is made to maximize expected utility. In addition, the obstacle and number of pedestrians in the next cell is sensed, and the corresponding speed-and-lane decision is made.

2. For cells $t = 2$ until $t = N$, the following steps are repeated:
- Obstacles and the number of pedestrians in the next cell are assessed.
 - The expected utility is computed.
 - Speed-and-lane decisions maximizing expected utility are transmitted to the ADS controller.
 - The ADS moves to the next cell.

3. Upon arriving at cell $t = N$, the trip concludes, and the attained utility is computed.

The code in Python to reproduce the experiments is available at https://github.com/roinaveiro/preferences_ads (accessed March 21, 2021).

Endnotes

¹ This refers to the ethical perspective asserting that the morality of an action depends on its consequences. An action has no ethical character in and of itself.

² This refers to the ethical framework emphasizing the inherent morality of action. An action is right or wrong in and of itself, regardless of its consequences.

³ See <https://h2020-trustonomy.eu/> (accessed March 21, 2021).

⁴ This refers to the ethical philosophy claiming that inequality is unjust (O’Neill 2008).

⁵ This refers to the ethical perspective stating that individual rights are supreme to other factors; individuals have the fundamental right to control their own destiny.

⁶ Utilitarianism is a form of consequentialism asserting that ethical actions maximize the collective well-being of all affected individuals.

⁷ Ethical egoism is a form of consequentialism asserting the morality of self-interest maximization.

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William N. Caballero is an assistant professor of mathematical sciences at the United States Air Force Academy. His research emphasizes both normative and descriptive approaches to game theory and decision theory as well as the utilization of mathematical programming and Markov decision processes in varied applications. Dr. Caballero holds a PhD in operations research from the Air Force Institute of Technology and is a board member of the *INFORMS Military and Security Society*.

Roi Naveiro is a postdoctoral researcher at the Institute of Mathematical Sciences. He earned his doctorate in statistical science and operations research from Complutense University of Madrid in 2020. Dr. Naveiro's technical interests and expertise are far-reaching, including such diverse areas as Bayesian forecasting, adversarial machine learning, game theory, and risk analysis.

David Ríos Insua is the AXA-ICMAT Chair in Adversarial Risk Analysis, research professor in risk analysis at the Institute of Mathematical Sciences, and member of the Spanish Royal Academy of Sciences. He is a professor of operations research and statistics at the Complutense University of Madrid (on leave). His research interests include decision analysis, Bayesian statistics, and risk analysis.